

TAILORED POLYMER NETWORKS BY SEQUENTIAL THIOL-ENE PHOTOPOLYMERIZATION

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Experimental design

- Three tetrathiol macromonomer (MM) were synthesized by thiol-Michael addition of TMPTMP (red) over PEGDA (green) of three different Mn
- Twelve networks were photopolymerized with benzoin ethyl ether (1%_w) comprising PEGDA of three different Mn, with or without TEGDVE, and with tetrathiol macromonomers (alternating structure) or without (uncontrolled structure)
- Each of the twelve networks was studied by DSC, DMTA and ATR FT-IR.

	S Mn(PEGDA)	M Mn(PEGDA)	L Mn(PEGDA)
3PEGDA + 2TMPTMP	Uncontrolled PEG _S	Uncontrolled PEG _M	Uncontrolled PEG _L
2PEGDA + MM	Alternating PEG _S	Alternating PEG _M	Alternating PEG _L
1PEGDA + 2TEGDVE + 2TMPTMP	Uncontrolled PEG _S -co-TEG	Uncontrolled PEG _M -co-TEG	Uncontrolled PEG _L -co-TEG ₇₀₀
2TEGDVE + MM	Alternating PEG _S -co-TEG	Alternating PEG _M -co-TEG	Alternating PEG _L -co-TEG

Concept

Ideal Alternating PEG-co-TEG network

- No consecutive PEG segments
- No terminal acrylate functionality
- All TMPTMP are bonded to one, and only one, PEG unit
- TEGDVE does not homopolymerize

Heat of reaction per thiol: homopolymerization

- Increasing PEGDA length correlates with increasing $-\Delta H/\text{mol S}$. The opposite was expected.
- The increase in $-\Delta H/\text{mol S}$ is caused by an increase in undesired acrylate homopolymerization.
- All PEG networks exhibit the same Tg, which reinforces the homopolymerization hypothesis. Both are tacky due to low thiol conversion.
- The effect is not observed in Alternating PEG-co-TEG, because homopolymerization of vinyl ethers is much slower than their thiol addition.